

**WORKSHOP REPORT:
CONTRIBUTIONS OF REGENERATIVE
AGRICULTURE AND ECOLOGICAL
RESTORATION IN THE MEDITERRANEAN**

IEMed - CREAM - AECID

ABSTRACT

This report synthesizes the outcomes of the international workshop held in Barcelona (26–27 June 2025), which convened 35 experts from ten Mediterranean countries to examine how regenerative agriculture and ecological restoration can address the region’s escalating environmental and socio-economic pressures. Participants identified shared challenges—including soil degradation, water scarcity, climate-driven extremes, biodiversity loss, and rural vulnerability—and mapped existing practices that are already contributing to more resilient and sustainable landscapes. The workshop also highlighted the institutional, economic, environmental, cultural, and knowledge barriers that impede wider adoption of these solutions. Building on collective expertise, the report outlines priority knowledge needs and opportunities for cooperation at local, national, and regional scales. As the first of two complementary deliverables, it provides an evidence-informed foundation for future dialogue, capacity-building, and policy innovation aimed at advancing a common Mediterranean vision for regenerative agriculture and ecological restoration.

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INTRODUCTION

The Mediterranean basin is among the regions most exposed to climate and environmental change, facing faster warming than the global average, increasing droughts, advancing desertification, and biodiversity loss. These pressures affect both people and ecosystems: water scarcity threatens agriculture, soil degradation undermines food security, and rural depopulation reshapes landscapes. The drivers and impacts differ across the basin—while the southern shore faces overgrazing and desertification under fragile governance settings, the northern shore grapples with land abandonment, intensive agriculture, and unsustainable consumption patterns.

In this context, regenerative agriculture and ecological restoration are gaining attention as approaches that protect biodiversity, rebuild soils, enhance resilience, and sustain livelihoods. They also align with international and regional frameworks such as the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration, the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, and the EU Green Deal.

Under the umbrella of the **Masar al'an programme** of the Spanish Agency for International Development Cooperation (AECID), the **Centre for Ecological Research and Forestry Applications (CREAF)** and the **European Institute of the Mediterranean (IEMed)** have initiated a collaboration to advance these approaches in the Mediterranean. As a first step, the three institutions organized an international workshop in Barcelona on **26–27 June 2025**, bringing together **35 experts from 10 Mediterranean countries**, including representatives of governments, research institutions, civil society, international organizations, and the private sector.

Discussions focused on identifying recurrent drivers of degradation—such as climate change, overgrazing, water mismanagement, and the erosion of traditional knowledge—while also recognizing promising practices already being applied in different contexts. Participants further examined the institutional, economic, cultural, and knowledge barriers to scaling up solutions. The workshop was designed as the launch of a broader process of dialogue, co-production of knowledge, and capacity-building to foster cooperation and inspire policy innovation.

A second workshop, planned for a southern Mediterranean country, was envisioned to build on these foundations by showcasing solutions, highlighting best practices, and discussing options for implementation and scaling-up. The organization of this follow-up event, however, remains under consideration.

This report summarizes the outcomes of the Barcelona workshop. It does not provide a comprehensive scientific assessment but rather reflects the collective expertise and perspectives of diverse Mediterranean stakeholders. It presents:

- The main environmental and socio-economic challenges identified.
- Existing practices and solutions.
- Institutional, economic, environmental, cultural, and knowledge barriers hindering progress.
- Knowledge needs to advance the transition.
- Opportunities for multilevel cooperation.

This document is the first of two deliverables associated with the workshop. While this report focuses on capturing the results and discussions as they emerged from the participants, a second, complementary report offers a more policy-oriented analysis of these findings to inform decision-making and future regional cooperation. Together, these efforts aim to guide the design of cooperation projects, national and regional strategies, and international processes. Ultimately, they contribute to a common Mediterranean vision for regenerative agriculture and ecological restoration—one that bridges North and South, integrates traditional and scientific knowledge, and places farmers, practitioners, and local communities at the center of transformative change.

RESULTS

STRUCTURE

The coding frame below results from supplementing the preliminary coding with insights from the workshop data, to create more categories of secondary coding where applicable. This inductive approach allows for a more complete coding frame.

PRIMARY	SECONDARY	INDICATORS
Challenges	Environmental	Issues for nature
	Socio-economic	Issues for people
Existing solutions	Regen. agriculture	Farming to regenerate nature
	Eco. restoration	Practices to rehabilitate landscape
	Society-wide	Initiatives involving larger society
Barriers	Institutional	Policy/regulation preventing solutions
	Economic	Finances/markets preventing solutions
	Environmental	Environmental concerns preventing sol.
	Custom	Customs preventing solutions
Knowledge needs	Knowledge	Wrong/lack of knowledge preventing sol.
	Technical	Necessity for education/training
Collaboration	Transfer	Optimising use existing knowledge
	Follow-up	Within the scope of this project
	International	Large-scale with international partners
	National	Initiative required on national scale
	Local	Projects best suited to local scale

CHALLENGES

As part of this first category, inputs are collected that relate to problems and issues for both natural and human life. These challenges result from a variety of causes but are categorised based on what they affect: environment or society and economy.

ENVIRONMENTAL

Soil degradation is reported because of salinisation, nutrient depletion, organic matter loss, plastic pollution, over-abundance of nitrates/pesticides, overgrazing, and land abandonment. This results in, among others, **poor water retention, erosion, and biodiversity loss**.

Climate change effects such as drought, desertification, extreme/unpredictable weather, and invasive species are observed. These effects are said to be further exacerbated by human mismanagement (see unsustainable practices below).

Water scarcity issues, like groundwater depletion, sea water intrusion, and competition for water between people, farming, and other uses, are reported by participants to affect landscapes across the Mediterranean.

Land-use trade-off dynamics, for example around dryland, ecological restoration, and agriculture are seen as problematic. There, unsustainable practices like large-scale monoculture and loss of traditional grazing systems further **damage ecosystems**.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC

Agriculture is under pressure from water scarcity and reduced rainfall, which shorten agricultural seasons, reduce yields, and threaten livelihoods. This is expressed as particularly problematic in regions where agriculture is the main economic activity.

Ability to maintain and take care of land is reduced due to biodiversity loss, rural depopulation (urbanisation dynamics), and land fragmentation.

Pressures on useable land and water are reported to be worsened by broader societal problems such as poverty, illiteracy, and climate migration.

Mismanagement in terms of inadequate preparation for water extremes, market forces being ignored in policy, land grabbing by foreign investors, and dumping of synthetic fertilisers, is named as a set of dynamics that pose further challenges to societies.

EXISTING SOLUTIONS

In this second category, responses are reported that mention best practices in solving the challenges mentioned above. The solutions are categorised based on the domain they relate to: regenerative agriculture, ecological restoration, or all of society.

REGENERATIVE AGRICULTURE

The following **practices** are reported to have positive effects (if used consciously): reduced tillage, crop diversification (native/non-native resistant varieties), intercropping, integrating livestock (including controlled grazing), sustainable (ferti-) irrigation (including water/sludge re-use), creating terraces, (rock) mulching, using bio-waste fertilisers, syntropic agroforestry / conservation agriculture (more holistic), soil carbon capture, dedicated plant nurseries.

The following **tools and approaches** are reported as useful: participatory methods such as living labs, replication labs, and peer-to-peer learning, guided by advisors/trainers as a neutral actor, as well as the use of technology (AI, remote sensing, smart monitoring) and traditional systems (e.g. rotation).

The following **institutional support systems** are mentioned as having positive effects: sustainability incentives (e.g. providing free trees), increasingly relevant carbon credits, national programmes (e.g., Morocco's Green Generation), international networks and databases of good practices.

ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION

Participants report positive experiences with the following **techniques**: planting in arid areas, managed grazing, wetland restoration, sponge-soil restoration and biodiversity stimulation approaches.

The following **means of support** are indicated as useful to complement the mentioned techniques: international best-practice databases (FAO / EU), circular bioeconomy principles, wild gene banks, and integration with renewable energy plans.

SOCIETY-WIDE

Participants indicated positive experiences with the following whole-of-society **approaches**: setting up integrated water and waste management systems, engaging market actors / dynamics (creating labels, value chain involvement), using traditional knowledge, including gender, centralising nature-based solutions, prioritising education and awareness, capitalising on rural value chain opportunities, working with participatory spaces for co-creation, and seeking national/multinational collaboration (especially mutually-relevant exchange North-South).

LIST OF EXISTING INITIATIVES MENTIONED

Initiative	Actor(s)	Scope	Link
Agricultura Regenerativa platform for regenerative agriculture knowledge-sharing and mapping	Asociación de Agricultura Regenerativa	Spain	https://www.agriculturaregenerativa.es/
Agrytech Supporting innovative Lebanese startups with tech solutions for the agrifood sector	Berytech	Lebanon	https://berytch.org/programs/agrytech/
AU Soil Observatory platform for soil health monitoring	AU, EU, multi-stakeholder	Africa	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101218840
Center of Arab Women for Training and Research center of academic research and field studies relating to women's conditions	Multi-stakeholder	Middle-East	https://cawtar.org/en
Circular Bioeconomy Alliance funding, expertise, and know how to facilitate projects designed to accelerate the transition to circular bioeconomy	Multi-stakeholder	Global	https://circularbioeconomyalliance.org/
EU PRIMA joint programme to support	EU, member states, partner countries	Mediterranean	https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/resea

food systems and water resources			rch-area/environment/prima_en
EU FarmBook platform, gathering and sharing agriculture and forestry knowledge	EU, multi-stakeholder	Europe	https://welcome.eufarmbook.eu/
Generation Green 2020-2030 strategy for conservation agriculture, complemented by 'Forests of Morocco'	Moroccan Government	Morocco	https://www.ada.gov.ma/en/news/his-majesty-king-mohammed-vi-launches-new-agricultural-strategy-generation-green-2020-2030
Hub del Norte organisation helping communities with regenerative practices to be more resilient	Savory Institute	North Spain	https://www.hubdelnorte.com/
International Compost Awareness Week	Compost Foundation	Global	https://www.compostfoundation.org/ICAW/ICAW-Home
Massire strengthening agricultural and rural innovation systems in oases and arid regions	Multi-stakeholder	Maghreb	https://en.massire.net/
NATAE foster agroecological transition	EU, multi-stakeholder	North Africa	https://www.natae-agroecology.eu/
Regenera.cat project to expand regenerative agriculture and viticulture in Catalonia	CREAF	Catalonia	https://regenera.creaf.cat/
ResAlliance project to engage with farmers and foresters to share knowledge and increase landscape resilience	EU (EFI), multi-stakeholder	Mediterranean	https://www.resalliance.eu/
UN FERM geospatial platform and registry of restoration initiatives	UN (FAO), multi-stakeholder	Global	https://ferm.fao.org/
UN SHARP self-evaluation tool for smallholder farmers and pastoralists to assess own climate resilience	UN (FAO)	Global	https://www.fao.org/land-water/land/land-governance/land-resources-planning-toolbox/category/details/fr/c/1043149/
Water Re-use in agriculture, forests, general consumption, national and ReWater	Governments, IWMI	MENA	

WOCAT global network on sustainable land management promoting documentation and knowledge sharing for adaptation, innovation and decision-making	Multi-stakeholder	Global	https://wocat.net/en/
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BARRIERS

As part of this third category, contributions are reported that share obstructions to the implementation of the solutions mentioned above. These barriers are divided into five types relating to the nature of the obstruction: institutional, economic, environmental, custom, and knowledge / awareness.

INSTITUTIONAL

Decision making is often experienced as top-down, with little influence by farmers, and much dominance by traditional agricultural-lobbies, leading to political unwillingness to deal with specific environmental issues such as pollution.

In terms of **coordination and consistency**, participants expressed barriers related to weak, fragmented, or unpredictable government policies, which are often poorly enforced, especially in contexts of much political fragility, and which are little coherent across the Mediterranean.

Regulatory hurdles and bureaucracy often limit action and innovation, specifically with regard to (organic) waste management and re-use, as well as start-ups and international trade in some contexts.

Inadequate governance and unwillingness to share knowledge and provide support, among others in solving land fragmentation and regulating carbon markets, sometimes stimulating wrong practices and often leading to distrust in authorities and policies.

ECONOMIC

The shift to more sustainable practices faces **profitability issues** because of its long return on investment caused by high land costs, lack of financial support at the start, market preference for unsustainable crops and large-scale, high technology costs, and limited equipment and workforce, especially for small farms and in the South.

In relation to wider **value chain and market mechanisms**, participants identify barriers relating to insufficient marketing and certification, greenwashing risks, imbalances in value chains profits, public and private funding shortages (especially South Mediterranean), and competition with other sectors.

ENVIRONMENTAL

The shift to sustainable practices in some cases also obstructed by **factors relating to the environment**, such as the high energy costs to treat wastewater or desalinate, competition with

renewable energy projects over land or water, basic needs of soil for recovery, and limited options for crop variety due to climate conditions.

CUSTOM

Resistance to regeneration and restoration sometimes comes from **generational or cultural practices**, which can for example be inherited ways of land use from previous generations, or religious constraints on water re-use. Similarly, complexity to reach community decision, societal norms that exclude women or youth, land inheritance issues, and long-standing scepticism toward official guidance can obstruct change.

KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS

Participants express **low levels of knowledge and awareness** about sustainable practices and their market labelling, especially among farmers and consumers, due to, among others, poor translation of science to practice, weak or non-innovative agricultural education, short-term vision, insufficient knowledge uptake on traditional practices, urban–rural disconnect and fragmentation of solutions more generally.

KNOWLEDGE NEEDS

In the fourth category, responses are collected that express which knowledge is required to overcome the barriers, implement the solutions, and/or address the challenges mentioned above. These knowledge needs are categorised as new technical knowledge that needs to be created, or existing knowledge that needs to be transferred.

TECHNICAL

Participants express the need for **holistic, applied and multi-stakeholder science** that can produce updated data to support the shift to sustainable practices, including knowledge creation on native and foreign resistant species, including attention for soil-water nexus, documenting traditional practices, scaling methods, and indicators tailored to different contexts.

TRANSFER

There is a need for platforms and labs in which **science–practice collaboration** can take place, working with accessible knowledge formats in terms of language, providing farmer, consumer and policymaker education, and training for intermediaries in advisor roles.

Trust-building needs to take place, ensuring successful science uptake in policy-making and by implementing communities, in combination with awareness campaigns.

COLLABORATION

The final category displays proposals for future action relating to regenerative agriculture and ecological restoration. These opportunities for collaboration can either be a follow-up of the current project of workshops, or part of broader action at the international, national, or local level.

FOLLOW-UP

As **short-term and passive** follow-up actions, participants recommend documenting the workshop results and making them publicly available, as well as producing a shorter document with resulting recommendations, such as a whitepaper. Outputs by the project could also focus on an economic narrative for regenerative and restorative practices and ways to unify traditional and modern methods.

If the project takes on a more **long-term and active** role, it is recommended to assist in the training of trainers/advisors/champions, facilitate further North-South exchanges, help in expanding the scale of living/replication labs across borders, or even advocate for the actions below, but also to conduct good stakeholder mapping to prevent replication of existing initiatives.

INTERNATIONAL

Multi-national action is recommended, making use of new or existing platform organisations, to **coordinate the shift** to sustainable practices across the Mediterranean, including through building large-scale participatory multi-stakeholder platforms, scaling-up living/replication labs, harmonising sustainability and waste regulations, coordinating integration of the transition with international (e.g. EU, carbon markets) policies, financially stimulating specific transitions, defining official data/standards, and harmonising data collection.

NATIONAL

State governments are recommended to facilitate **multi-stakeholder projects that align national with international priorities and co-create strategy**, for example by providing policy for land fragmentation and soil classification, strengthening extension services, helping in sustainable capacity building allowing for contract farming, and conducting national awareness campaigns.

LOCAL

On the local level, engagement with all stakeholders is recommended to **tailor national and international strategies and shared best practices to specific contexts**, for example by promoting regenerative agriculture as attractive and profitable, supporting cooperatives, addressing social/gender inequality, guide farmers on practical solutions, and even local-to-local collaboration where (international) consensus is difficult.

KEY THEMES FOR THE NEXT PHASE

1. Scaling Demonstration & Living Labs

→ Prioritize applied experimentation and direct farmer participation.

2. Establishing Legal & Financial Frameworks

→ Formalize regenerative agriculture and fund the transition.

3. Bridging the Knowledge Gap

→ Expand networks of trained technicians, accessible farmer education, and youth inclusion.

4. Creating Regional Mechanisms for Policy Alignment

→ Leverage cross-border collaboration and institutions like FAO to coordinate action.

5. Elevating Regenerative Agriculture in Public Perception

→ Change the narrative to highlight regeneration as a future-proof investment.

OTHER TABLES AND STICKY NOTES

STICKY NOTES

- Develop cost-action on regenerative agriculture
- EARA – European Alliance for Regenerative Agriculture (Ana Digón)
- Replication initiatives map Spanish Association of Regenerative Agriculture
- Harmonise data collection and sharing
- Analysis of policies at national / regional level
- Position project strategically with on-going policy/programmes
- Incorporate the WEF concept (and related actors)
- National strategy resulting from farmer needs/living labs
- Develop indicators adapted to southern countries
- REGEN label project (CREAF) as start Mediterranean conversation
- Develop business models around regenerative agriculture
- Be flexible in regenerative agriculture definition
- Make use of existing data bases and platforms
- National regulation regenerative agriculture
- Connect regenerative agriculture to Mediterranean culture (cooking, social, etc.)

MAIN IDEAS AND PARKING POINT

- White paper with key messages
- Another network? → expand existing
- Share findings
- Don't start from zero
- Disseminating good practices → FERM (FAO)

ANALYSIS RESULTS

CHALLENGES

ENVIRONMENTAL

- Spoiled soil retains less water, more evaporation, drought cycle
- Salinisation, depleted nutrients, soil degradation, too little organic matter
- Trade-off land use dry land/restoration/agriculture (agri > dry land, but degradation)
- Focus on short-term gains in agriculture affects biodiversity (Tunisia)
- Over-use of nitrate fertilisers, especially pig origin (Catalonia) affects water quality
- Desertification through climate change, lack rain and mismanagement, overgrazing
- Use of pesticides in agriculture damaging for biodiversity
- More extreme weather events, unpredictable, are challenges for nature and people
- Ground water depletion and retention, consequences for nature and people
- Sea water intrusion, shallow ground water, salinity (Nile delta, Cap Bon Tunisia)
- Challenges of overgrazing, abandonment have different consequences north/south
- Wind/water erosion
- Climate change and human action brings invasive species
- Large-scale agriculture is loss for society and nature in long term
- Loss traditional arrangements grazing create land degradation
- Soil pollution from agricultural plastics (e.g. greenhouses)

SOCIO-ECONOMIC

- Irrigation – not enough water available to irrigate, less rain also less agriculture season, less food production possible
- Consequences of biodiversity loss become more visible to society (cutting trees)
- Land fragmentation, rural depopulation leads to land less taken care of, less food
- Market forces not included in discussion
- In North: lack preparation water extremes (scarcity/floods)
- Agriculture is main economic activity in some regions and threatened by drought
- Climate migration due to more difficult living and agriculture conditions
- Works hand-in-hand with poverty, marginality, migration, literacy, etc.
- Less land, more degraded available for people
- Competition population/farming over ground water
- Dumping synthetic fertilisers north south
- Land grabbing by large foreign investment funds

EXISTING SOLUTIONS

REGENERATIVE AGRICULTURE

- Water and sludge re-use (also waste water), but carefully (fertiliser elements)
- More resistant/local crops, diversification, but also non-native resistant
- Less tillage (1 mln hectares Morocco), rock mulching, controlled grazing
- Living labs, participatory approaches have proven very useful, especially long-term
- Advisors and peer-to-peer learning as neutral force between scientists and farmers
- Ferti-irrigation, injecting fertiliser in irrigation (local government Valencia)
- Technology to make more resilience, and revive traditional (e.g. rotation systems)
- Morocco/Algeria have some EU/prima initiatives agro-ecology and -forestry with feedback processes, important multi-stakeholder element
- Successful projects using data to investigate best ways of multinational education
- Capturing water, terraces, moist in soil layers, works in Spain
- Intercropping (e.g. faba beans x barley) can be useful for weed reduction
- Integrating livestock in farming can be positive locally (managed grazing, soil regeneration, biodiversity), but large-scale difficult, combi pastures and crop covers
- Replication lab (>locations, >methods) = expansion living lab for replication good practices, EU Farmbook for generative practices collection, EU Green deal support
- More sustainable irrigation (dripping), recharge wells, prevent evaporation
- Nurseries preserve crops (Yemen), creation of new resistant crops (Morocco cactae)
- Sustainability incentives such as free trees and irrigation systems
- Already carbon credits working (example phosphor company paying sus. agri)
- Mixing of different bio-waste for fertiliser, but difficult food regulation
- AI and remote sensing could be useful but still requires good guidance, same smart real-time monitoring
- Conservation agriculture (Lebanon, Morocco, FAO): less soil disturbance, residue management, rotation <https://ferm.fao.org/>
- Research/entrepreneur co-develop alternative fertilisers (Berytech Lebanon)
- Syntropic agro-forestry many advantages, easier agri in forest than reverse
- 4 per mille strategy increasing carbon capture in soil
- Examples Spain: agriculturaregenerativa.es, other: Sharb tool (multistakeholder)
- Morocco 'Green Generation' and 'Conservation Agriculture' elaborate plans
- CREAF Regenera project shows actual benefits costs of production
- Oasis well preserved agro-ecology hotspots with much experience Morocco (COP22 initiative)
- Networks of regenerative agriculture exist in multiple countries by use of champions
- Replication initiatives map Spanish Association of Regenerative Agriculture

ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION

- Planting (crops/vegetation) in arid areas where water is available (Nile delta)

- Hub del Norte and Ale Hub projects restoring Nile and Sahel desert with soil restoration (sponge) and biodiversity principles
- Managed grazing can be good landscape restoration tool
- Restoration of wetlands
- FAO eco. Restoration practices success database: <https://wocat.net/en/projects-and-countries/projects/costs-and-benefits-slm-technologies/>
- Principles for regenerative landscape: circularbioeconomyalliance.org
- Res-Alliance project (EFI Med) traditional/local landscape resilience (EU database)

SOCIETY-WIDE

- Integrated systems of (rain/waste) water management and re-use (New Cities Cairo, forests Saudi), closing waste cycle
- Market representatives can be part of the discussion, also in creating a label
- In South more experience on extreme weather exists, which North can profit from
- Best experiences local change of mindset is inspiring, supporting, showcasing with peer-to-peer learning and projects
- Women work in ‘transformation’ making agri products ready for broad use (Lebanon)
- Traditional knowledge can be useful in some cases, like traditional water collection
- FAO provides land use planning guidance against fragmentation, poverty, etc.
- Societal appreciation food production and biodiversity (Italy)
- Opportunities in value chain to integrate profitable employment for rural areas
- Austria local initiatives of self collection, composting and reusing biowaste - ICAW – International compost awareness week
- Safe spaces of multi-stakeholder co-creation of sustainable practices, participatory
- Good databases of best practices being developed (FAO, EU)
- Nature based solutions (e.g. mangroves) to treat waste water and sludge
- Preserving wild gene bank vegetation for resilience
- Tunisia elaborate more-year strategy soil/forest conservation, focus water
- Soil research, monitoring, action projects (AU Soil Africa, Global Soil Laboratory) useful in Mediterranean context
- Planned grazing integrated in renewable energy plans
- LandBank programme for mentorship and job opportunities young people
- Massire (Horizon): practices, living labs, replication en.massire.net/presentation/
- NATAE: overview agro-ecology with FAO principles <https://www.natae-agroecology.eu/>
- Tunisia: multi-stakeholder co-creation process, bottom-up, water issues
- Involvement women in advisor training has given positive results, paradigm shift (Arab Women in Training and Research, Moroccan Women Farmers Association)

BARRIERS

INSTITUTIONAL

- Wildfire prevention necessary, but forests protected by law (Morocco and Tunisia)
- Different environmental policies and rules of sustainability and waste valorisation, though situation might differ, or lack (MENA), same for use organic amend. in soil
- Some regions of Mediterranean, farmers have no decision-making power due to political circumstances, or no water access at all (Palestine), other regions fragile (Lebanon: abandoned lands)
- Creation of label together with market representatives, difficult to define
- Bureaucracy and regulation are often hurdle for sustainable farmers (multi-level) and for knowledge exchange, regulation often too unpredictable for long-term
- Lack of coherence in policy and regulation across countries and authorities (especially South), good plans exist, but do not easily get integrated in local practice
- Governments not supportive in land abandonment issue, nor novel agriculture ideas, lack or failing extension services that collaborate and guide farmers, lack in capacity regulation and guidance, no long-term planning
- Focus on subsidies over transformation in land use, sometimes stimulation wrong practices (subsidise grain to lower price gives more monoculture) and large firms
- Good guidance necessary on practices of AI and remote sensing
- Loss traditional arrangements grazing create land degradation
- Too much land fragmentation for large-scale solutions (different north/south), land tenure affects willingness/ability to invest in soil (FAO)
- Unwillingness to share knowledge north-south
- Lack proper waste regulation
- Whenever solutions are proposed, too much top-down for successful impl.
- Lack willingness to address pollution, gives lack facilities available for recycling
- Interests of traditional agricultural companies much represented (e.g. EU)
- Urbanisation and drain young people makes innovation agriculture difficult
- Innovation (e.g. new crops) comes with practical doubts, insufficient guidance
- Legislation start-ups and in/export taxes makes international working difficult
- Distrust towards government over past unfair practices with planting (Morocco)
- South Mediterranean globally, not very much priority, and lacks policy coherence like EU
- Policy making not enough based in science, agendas stakeholders not aligned, more political/industrial agendas (influence powerful agri lobbies), opposing sectoral interests
- Carbon markets useful, but little guided/regulated
- Lack powerful Mediterranean institution/organisation

ECONOMIC

- Competition of regenerative agriculture with other sectors (tourism, urban)
- Financing and involvement of all market stakeholders crucial
- Cost of externalities not included in the final product price

- Unsustainable crops often based on local market demands, even if import possible\
- Land access is expensive, even for farmer families, only interest change if own land
- Some regions struggle technology implementation and cannot compete (Lebanon)
- Without support often easiest way is chosen, difficulty is transition period profitable
- Priorities in re-use of water are different north/south, sometimes only for rich (Egypt)
- Introduction livestock in agriculture difficult because of specialisation
- No access/financial means for required machinery/smart tech, guidance agriculture (difference north/south)
- Lack of equipment to monitor performance of agricultural methods
- Increasing gap commercially viable vs. more sustainable crops
- Development of smart technology too fast for effective agri implementation
- Market supports sustainable products, but need to ensure good marketing and organisation and certification, but still attention for right sustainable dynamics in market, risk greenwashing (soils)
- Intensification necessary in agriculture limits diversity and regeneration
- Farms too small/big for easy transition/technology implementation
- Transfer period too unsure, long return on investment, no incentives for change
- In South, funding is larger issue than workforce
- Unfair revenue from farming in market makes change difficult, sometimes even stop, imbalance value chain

ENVIRONMENTAL

- Cleaning/desalinizing of water for (re)use costs much energy
- Competition of regenerative agriculture with green energy (solar farms) over space
- Limited variety crops/trees/seeds available for regenerative agriculture because limiting climate conditions
- Many solutions need water (herb/crop cover), difficult with limited water
- Basic land conditions necessary for regenerative agriculture (organic matter), recovering takes time

CUSTOM

- Religious constrains on water re-use (drinking dirty water in Morocco, fatwas)
- Habits and mindset local people are not easy to change, much resistance, farmers' customs come from inherited knowledge (conservatism/ancestorial practices)
- Community ownership makes decision making difficult
- Women not included in decision making
- Generational change difficult with little land access people without tradition
- Gender and youth often experience more difficulty participating, lack promotion
- Working with family gives false impression financial viability

- Women often much but unfairly involved (salary/labour, decision making, specific jobs, land use rights, knowledge availability), in some cases more open to change, but maybe not as bad as other sectors, but simple parity without context not solve
- Much regional differences/disparities and stigma for innovation make difficult
- Some communities sceptical of academic/government guidance, prefer view

KNOWLEDGE/AWARENESS

- Solutions too much focussed on single domain/sector, holistic vision necessary
- 'ivory tower' separate narratives science/practice
- Little understanding sustainable water and pesticide use among farmers, just like correct use of livestock for regeneration
- Neighbouring farms see regenerative methods next door as an over-spill threat
- Short vs long-term issues as seen by farmers, convincing sustainable difficult
- Little knowledge/awareness sustainability and labels (not always strict bio vs. Regular) by consumers
- Finding more adapted crops sometimes very difficult
- Policy makers lack knowledge soil sustainability
- Lack translation (language and simplicity) research to accessible formats
- Avoid one-size-fits-all solutions, often not mindful of local context
- Too little land management – technical education with valuable knowledge
- Agricultural education little innovative (regenerative) and not coherent
- Too little knowledge/evidence about advantages traditional practices
- Subsidies to stimulate agri-workforce unsuccessful, attracts unskilled
- Disconnect urban/rural

KNOWLEDGE NEEDS

TECHNICAL

- Science needs to be brave and cutting-edge
- Knowledge- and practice-based holistic science, with many stakeholders
- Ensure production updated data that can help farmers take good decisions
- Knowledge on resistant native and foreign species to know what to grow
- Invest in further collaborative research on regenerative agriculture with prototypes
- Knowledge production on traditional practices' advantages (documenting)
- Lack knowledge on scaling practices, leading definitions, indicators, and data (flexible but useful)
- Focus on applied research
- Develop indicators suitable for southern countries

TRANSFER

- Guidance to authorities on importance and classification soil for use limits
- Situations in which science/practice discourses can come together (labs), making more farmers understand usefulness sustainable land use, participatory debates
- Sharing of right data (and crops) with farmers so they can make good decisions
- Help convey information on sustainability choices and labels to consumers
- Help educate consumers on impact of certain products
- Create accessible information formats (language and simplicity) and training, also with narrative shift to economic interest farmers
- Agriculture education that integrates theory and practice
- Raise awareness importance sustainable practices with policy makers
- Train advisors in knowledge/skills to be better able to talk to farmers
- Raise awareness ecological restoration South
- Science uptake and follow-up by policy/communities crucial to not loose knowledge
- Soil-water nexus needs more attention (soil-enriching initiatives to retain water)
- Trust-building to regain confidence in science institutes

COLLABORATION

FOLLOW-UP

- Documenting workshop inputs and results so accessible for everybody
- Expand scale of practical learning (living labs, replication labs, advisors, peer-to-peer, study visits), but avoiding one-size-fits all solutions
- Training trainers (advisors, agricultural extension agents) can be good focus
- Expand north/south collaboration projects (multi-level exchange forums)
- In collaboration with FAO, land productivity research
- Ensure platform for sharing best practices (use existing e.g. FAO?)
- Allow labs and trials to be more long-term, scalability and replicability
- Involve all many stakeholders (value chain): private sector = scalability, finance, knowledge; labour unions; water users associations, safe meetings
- Invest in advisors that can transfer knowledge to and guide farmers
- Invest in trust-building, working with champions
- Necessity to holistic consider all factors relevant to issues
- Ensure involvement women and youth, can be drivers for innovation
- Exchange mutually beneficial knowledge North-South, platform like FAO FIRM
- Mapping of stakeholders (same GEF reporting) first step in moving forward, ensure collaboration, start from ways in which stakeholders can contribute with own capacity, do not start from scratch with new network, expand existing
- Contribute to narrative shift: from sustainable to economically/politically viable, include Mediterranean culture (food, social, etc.)
- Collaboration often small farmers, target big farms too to set example

- Projects should work at push but bring self-sustaining at some point
- Involving youth gives opportunity to blend traditional and modern approaches
- Responding to calls for proposals
- Network demonstration farms, capacity-building platform, knowledge-sharing hub, community of practice (regular meeting), identify priority themes
- Develop economic narrative (cost-action) on regenerative agriculture
- Analyse existing national/regional policies (WEFE), position project strategically
- REGEN project (CREAF) can serve as basis for Mediterranean conversation
- Disseminate findings and key messages with white paper

INTERNATIONAL

- Making use of living labs on larger scale, make national projects international (like PRIMA AquaMed project Algeria-Tunisia)
- Scheme of costs including price of externalities
- Work towards same regulation in mediterranean area of sustainability and waste
- Active policy that prioritises sustainable practices for public funds
- Creation of company/product sustainability ranking with rewards
- Expand North/South collaboration projects
- Consumer awareness programmes/campaigns
- Biodiversity preservation roadmap
- Coherent legislation in region to protect soils
- Invest in participatory multi-stakeholder platforms for innovation, data, best practices, learning, addressing social and gender equality with eye for local
- Find integration with EU Common Agricultural Policy Ecosystems and Green Deal, also with South
- Ensure coherent regulation around waste
- Mediterranean regional collaboration can be hub for multi-stakeholder collaboration
- Research, monitoring, access, education facility (observatory) on soil (but broader environmental science) in region, strengthen links research-policy-practice
- Ensure supporting market and ensuring mechanisms that will help transition (definition/certification regenerative agriculture) and coordination sectors
- Appropriate regional platform necessary to coordinate transfer
- Find way of financing transition and risks
- Define official definitions and data for all stakeholders to work with
- Projects on rural development can tie into other development themes
- Allow for carbon market to integrate with farmers to stimulate practices
- Working groups per topic and ecosystem inclusivity to include all people/nature
- Harmonise data collection and sharing

NATIONAL

- Work with multi-stakeholder approaches on national level, together with IOs (FAO facilitation), using good data/definitions (e.g. international)
- Classify soils to determine type and limits of use, public tool recommendation irrigation/fertirrigation pilot
- Align projects with national priorities, provide carrots/sticks to shape practices
- Learn from others in designing good extension services (France, Catalunya PATT)
- Policy addressing land fragmentation
- Make sure to involve multiple government departments
- Need capacity building strategy
- Work with farmers small, but certainly large (Morocco experience: connections)
- Work with contract farming (guaranteed sale to company needing product)
- Awareness campaigns focussing on all stakeholders are necessary (focus benefits)
- Action by all stakeholders, but financial backing transition by governments/private
- National strategies developed based on farmer/living lab input

LOCAL

- Creation of vision/awareness holistic view sustainable land use
- Making (regenerative)agriculture more attractive (sexy and profitable)
- Local governments involved in knowledge production
- Focus on local production, consumption and alternatives
- Participate in tailoring best practices to local context
- Promotion cooperative schemes for access to materials/machinery
- Need to guide farmers in finding practical solutions to practical doubts
- Address social/gender inequality with eye for local and empowerment
- Farmer collective collaboration (e.g. cooperatives) essential in implementation
- Help translate materials to right and easy language
- Trans-local collaboration can be employed for politicised issues sometimes
- Working with local governments to create context-specific roadmaps

CONCLUSION

The Barcelona workshop confirmed that regenerative agriculture and ecological restoration are central to building resilience in the Mediterranean. Despite significant environmental and socio-economic challenges, participants highlighted a wide range of practices and experiences that show tangible benefits for soils, water, biodiversity, and rural livelihoods. At the same time, the discussions revealed persistent institutional, economic, cultural, and knowledge barriers that hinder wider adoption.

Moving forward, bridging these gaps will require sustained collaboration across scales—local, national, and regional—anchored in participatory approaches, trust-building, and the integration of scientific and traditional knowledge. Participants emphasized the importance of demonstration projects, legal and financial frameworks that reward regenerative practices, and regional mechanisms to align policies and exchange lessons between the northern and southern shores.

This report is a first step in capturing the diversity of perspectives and solutions emerging from across the Mediterranean. Its findings will feed into a broader policy-oriented analysis and serve as a foundation for further dialogue, cooperation, and action. Ultimately, the momentum created in Barcelona can help inspire a shared Mediterranean vision: one where regenerative agriculture and ecological restoration are recognized not only as environmental necessities, but also as pathways for prosperity, social cohesion, and peace with nature.

WORKSHOP INFORMATION: AGENDA AND LIST OF PARTICIPANTS

PROGRAM OF THE FIRST WORKSHOP, BARCELONA 26TH AND 27TH JUNE 2025

DAY 1 – THURSDAY 26 JUNE, 2025	
TIME	PROGRAMME
8:30 – 9:30	Morning coffee and registration
9:30 – 9:45	Welcome and introduction to the workshop: IEMed, CREAM, AECID
9:45 - 10:00	“Ice breaker” dynamic: CREAM
10:00 – 10:30	Keynote presentations: CREAM scientists
10:30 – 12:45	<p>Workshop session 1: Understanding the Context and Laying the Groundwork</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explanation of the methodology: CREAM <p>QUESTIONS:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> What are the main environmental and socio-economic challenges threatening agricultural sustainability in the Mediterranean? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How are desertification and soil degradation affecting landscapes and communities in your region? What roles do climate change, overgrazing, and unsustainable land use play? How do these challenges vary between the northern and southern Mediterranean shores? Is it expected that food production will decrease in the countries on the southern shore of the Mediterranean? Is this a situation that is already occurring because of drought, climate change, or dependence on imports? What practices and experiences of regenerative agriculture and ecological restoration already exist in the Mediterranean region? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are there local responses to drought, water scarcity, or soil degradation using agroecological or restorative methods? How are farmers or land stewards addressing issues like biodiversity loss or declining soil fertility? Are there innovative approaches (e.g., composting, reforestation, water harvesting) that have worked well?
12:45 - 13:15	Debriefing and summary of session 1: CREAM

13:15 - 14:30	Lunch
14:30 – 16:30	<p>Workshop session 2: Identifying Barriers and Conditions for Change</p> <p>QUESTIONS:</p> <p>3. What are the main technical and environmental barriers to implementing or expanding regenerative and restorative practices?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there gaps in technical knowledge or access to training, especially around soil and water management? • Do policy, market, or governance structures support or hinder the adoption of sustainable practices? • How does waste mismanagement or land tenure affect your ability to restore degraded land? <p>4. What are the institutional, social, and economic barriers that limit the adoption of regenerative and restorative practices?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do policy frameworks, subsidies, or land tenure systems affect sustainable land management? • Are there disconnects between science, practice, and policy that need to be addressed? • How do social inequalities (e.g., gender, rural marginalization) influence access to resources and decision-making?
16:30 – 17:00	Debriefing and summary of session 2: CREAM
DAY 2 – FRIDAY 27 JUNE, 2025	
09:30 – 10:00	Recap from Day 1: CREAM
10:00 – 11:30	<p>Workshop session 3: Moving forward</p> <p>QUESTIONS:</p> <p>5. How can local & regional actors participate in this change of perspective?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are traditional knowledge systems being recognized or sidelined? • To what extent are local communities key to implementing regenerative practices? • How can awareness of the benefits of regenerative agriculture be raised among farmers, local communities and society at large? • What are the cultural or behavioral norms that need to be shifted? <p>6. What enabling conditions are needed to move toward collective action and co-design solutions across the Mediterranean region?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What kind of support or collaboration (local, national, cross-border) would help overcome existing barriers?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can the outcomes of this workshop guide the development of a regional vision or future initiative (e.g., pilot project, living lab)? • What themes or needs should be prioritized in the next phase of this conversation?
11:30 – 12:00	Coffee Break
12:00 – 13:00	Debriefing and summary of session 2: CREAM
13:00 – 13:30	Next steps: IEMed, CREAM
13:30 – 13:45	Conclusions and closing remarks: AECID
13:45 – 15:00	Lunch

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